

THE EMERGENCE OF MULTIPLE ENGLISHES TREND, DO WE NEED A STANDARD ENGLISH?

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Abstract: English has inevitably the global language that been used around the globe. According to Cristal there are approximately 1500 million people who use English from all sources; 750 million is first and second language speaker and the rest as foreign speaker. In the other word, there are one of the world population who are capable to use English. Interestingly, users of English as second and foreign language outnumbered the users of English as first language, which the ratio is 1:3 for native and non-native. Moreover, McArthur assumes that with the wide spread of new English trend, when they communicate together with their own New English, it will produce confusions and nonsenses among the speaker since they use unfamiliar English word in term of dialect and accents. To this purpose ministry of Singapore emphasizes the important of fostering standard English, not Singaporean English, especially in school to enable Singaporean communicate with people around the world. To sum up, standard English is now still urgent to be mastered since it is universally accepted for the world global communication.

Key words: English as international Language (EIL), Multiple Englishes, Standard English

INTRODUCTION

English has inevitably the global language that been used around the globe. According to Cristal there are approximately 1500 million people who use English from all sources; 750 million is first and second language speaker and the rest as foreign speaker(Crystal, 2003, p. 69). In the other word, there are one of the world population who are capable to use English. Interestingly, users of English as second and foreign language outnumbered the users of English as first language, which the ratio is 1:3 for native and non-native(Crystal, 2003, p. 69).

The development of English as global language links with the history of how English made across the globe. The spread of English was through the diaspora and power of the L1 country. The diaspora was to the isles around Britain such as Wales, Cornwall, Cumbria and southern Scotland. Afterward the large scale migrations to the North America beginning in 16th century and the Britain empire started expansion to the Africa, India and South Pacific through colonialization(Crystal, 2003, p. 30). As a result, English becomes powerful today and widely spread around the globe(Crystal, 2003, p. 76). Moreover, it supported by the globalization which dominated by the western hegemony through trading, influence trend and culture(Phillipson, 1992, p. 59).

Therefore, by the power that the English speaking country have, English teaching was later realized as a compulsory subject around the world including Indonesia. Since it becomes necessary the English teaching automatically turn in to commodity toward the Indonesian. The English teacher, of course, will have economic advantages by earning money to spread the language. When teaching English, the teacher consciously or unconsciously has become the agent of linguistic imperialism who extend the use of English. Indonesian society can be easily targeted as this nation is in the group of extended circle(Crystal, 2003, p. 60). English Language Teaching (ELT) can be a vital weapon to make this half-conscious society to provide agency service to compete the imperial competitors' for the sake of economic power benefit(Yusny, 2013, p. 94). In the other word, the original identity of the teacher can be bought by the dominant and powerful societies (English).

For these reasons, there is an urgent need of educating local practitioners of ELT to raise their awareness of any potential hidden agenda encapsulated within the English language pedagogy. In addition, ELT practitioners in Indonesia are required to be neutral; not to oppose and feel guilty of the profession. In the same time, ELT in Indonesia should have a commitment to benefit the local society to be able take active part in the continuing globalization positively. Language policy needs to be purposely strengthening the purism of the national language

and raised better nationalism, not putting “aggressive efforts to implement assimilative language policies and educational curricula”(Kachru, 2015, p. 166). Even though for the Indonesia context, Bahasa Indonesia is already hard-framed within the society, which unlikely becomes ‘killed’ by English (Crystal, 2003)

LITERATURE REVIEW

The economic power, technology and internet industry growth in English speaking country especially united states make English inevitable global language. Consequently, English is used by different people and of course different dialect which, in some cases, makes some features of English changed. As an example, in Singapore English there is an additional word “lah” after an utterance and word “kena” to change *be* in passive sentence(Mesthrie, 2010, p. 599). Furthermore, now the term New English has widely spread around the globe such as Nigerian English, Singapore English, African English, south Asian English etc(Platts, Weber, & Lian, n.d., p. 3). This is what crystal called as “linguistic change” as a consequence of the global language(Crystal, 2003, p. 142). When this language shift occurred, then it very important to know whether those varieties of English can be included into standard English.

Standard English functions as mutual intelligibility among the users all over the world. To this purpose standard English exclude local dialect, accepted as educational target and limited number of variation(Strevens, 1983). This standard English is used universally since it is accepted and understood among the English speaker around the world. For this reason, Plat, weber and lian suggested that English in multilingual countries ‘can be considered a *neutral language of communication*(Pennycook, 2002, p. 23). In the contrary, New English dominantly use local dialect and accents inasmuch as it promotes local identity(Crystal, 2003, p. 176). As a result, New Englishes are only used in particular country or area where the New Englishes occur.

In 16th century France has become the lingua franca around the Europe countries, at the time English speaker was only the isles around Britain. But it was predicted that English will take the role as global language by some factors. As a matter of fact, in 1767, at the time French became the language of international diplomacy, David Hume has assumed that by the solid and increasing development in America by the England diaspora will then make English take the control of global language(Crystal, 2003, p. 74; Hume, 1932). In addition, John Adams argued that English has been destined to become the next global language since the increasing population in America, economy development, multi-lateral connections made by America, and supported by the

influence of England empire colony around the world, eventually will make English as global language in the future. This prediction come to reality after 2 centuries when English has spread out and been used by almost 1500 million people around the globe(Crystal, 2003, p. 69). In recent situation, however, Chinese seemingly will take over the control of global language in the future.

The fundamental reason toward this view, of course massive economy development in china, whereas other countries are surviving their economy growth during the economy crisis in recent years. In fact, China gross domestic product (GDP) is in first rank above US and other English speaking countries(knoema, 2017). For this reason, Davis suggests that with only 30% in total English speaking country of world GDP and it likely will be lesser in future, it is urgent for English speaking country to learn other languages (Davis, 2003 as cited in Graddol, 2006, p. 62). In addition, there are more or less than 30 million people are already learning Mandarin around the globe and it is targeted to be 100 million people for the next few years(Graddol, 2006, p. 63). Furthermore, china government has actively support the interest of mandarin whether as second or foreign language through “Confucius Institute” which been built in some cities(Graddol, 2006, p. 63). Even these number is small in comparison toward English, with consistent growth and support from the

china government it is not impossible for mandarin to change the English position in the next few years.

Even tough, Mandarin is likely change the position of English as global language due to economy development, some historian belief that it will not happen in two or three generations change. For the comparison, English conquered French in battle of “global language” position for about two centuries. Similarly, mandarin will at least need the same time or even more to conquer English. Furthermore, despite economy power, there must be other supporting power that underlie a language to be a global language such as academic and media(“Will Chinese Replace English as the Global Language?,” 2017). English, in one hand, has been used academically in journals, books, university that make it familiarly used by the educational member around the globe. Mandarin, in the other hand, is limitedly used by university in China and Taiwan. Moreover, media is inevitably a mean of promoting the language and culture and English speaking country make use of media to spread out and promote the language through movie, talk show, news, music etc. in the contrary, we almost never, or even never, see china movie in cinema, or china song in our gadget. In short, economy power is inadequate enough, to make a language as global language due to the needs to other factors like academic and media.

Conclusion

Moreover, McArthur assumes that with the wide spread of new English trend, when they communicate together with their own New English, it will produce confusions and nonsenses among the speaker (McArthur, 1998, p. 22 as cited in Crystal, 2003, p. 167) since they use unfamiliar English word in term of dialect and accents. To this purpose ministry of Singapore emphasizes the important of fostering standard English, not Singaporean English, especially in school to enable Singaporean communicate with people around the world. To sum up, standard English is now still urgent to be mastered since it is universally accepted for the world global communication.

REFERENCE

- Kachru, B. B. (2015). Asian Englishes Today. *Saudi Med J*, 33, 3–8.
<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0703993104>
- Phillipson, R. (1992). Linguistic Imperialism.
- Yusny, R. (2013). ELT IN INDONESIAN CONTEXT : ISSUES, 1(1), 81–98.
- Crystal, D. (2003). *English as a global language Second edition*.
Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Mesthrie, R. (2010). New Englishes and the native speaker debate.

Language Sciences, 32(6), 594–601.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langsci.2010.08.002>

Pennycook, A. (2002). *ENGLISH AND THE DISCOURSES* (1st ed.).

New York: Routledge.

Platts, J., Weber, H., & Lian, H. M. (n.d.). *The New Englishes*. London:

Routledge.

Strevens, P. (1983). What is “Standard English?” Oxford.

Graddol, D. (2006). *English Next* (1st ed.). Plymouth: Latimer Trend &

Company Ltd.

Hume, D. (1932). *THE LETTERS OF DAVID HUME*. (J. Y. T. GREIG,

Ed.) (2nd ed.). London: Oxford University Press.

knoema. (2017). World GDP Ranking 2017, GDP by country.

Will Chinese Replace English as the Global Language? (2017).

Retrieved October 3, 2017, from

<https://learningenglish.voanews.com/a/will-chinese-replace-english-as-international-language/2554910.html>